

Deltaic depositional system in the Kutai Basin: an afterthought

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Abstract

The interaction of fluvial, tidal, and wave processes that developed in the Serravallian-Tortonian deposit of the Kutai Basin has been interpreted as a deltaic depositional system. This interpretation is debatable since the interaction of fluvial, tidal, and wave processes is potentially produced not only delta system. Estuary, strand plain, and other non-deltaic systems (e.g., strand plain, shoreface, lagoon, and barrier island) are possibly produced. In addition, those conditions have happened in the Modern Mahakam Delta. Consequently, fluvial, tides, and wave influence discrimination is the main factor in understanding the fluvial-marine transition zone. The challenge is that fluvial discharge coexists with tidal processes, making it challenging to identify the discrimination of importance of the fluvial, tides, and wave processes. It is essential to pay attention to the level of analysis and the scale of observations that will influence the interpretation of the scale of the depositional system in the regional context.

Fluvial proportion

A delta form where sediment-laden rivers enter oceans, enclosed seas, lakes, or lagoons (standing body of water) and supply more sediment than can be distributed by processes that operate within the receiving basin (Elliot, 2005). The result of that process is a shoreline migration and typically advances or prograde into the basin. By that definition, all deltas are, to some degree, fluvial-dominated.

Discrimination of fluvial, tides and wave influence is the main objective at observation. Ichnological and

sedimentological study in the modern Mahakam delta (Figure. 1) shows symptoms of fluvial domination's relative importance varies systematically through the river to marine transition (Arifullah, 2005). An increase in the tidal range also causes tidal action to penetrate farther inland, whereas an increase in fluvial discharge causes a decrease the tidal penetration. That situation happened not only in deltaic settings but also in all fluvial-marine transition zones (see Dalrymple et al. 2015; Fig. 1.2; Dalrymple and Choi, 2007, Fig. 9).

The northern distributaries of Modern Mahakam Delta a showed fluvial domination decline in the point when tidal action penetrates farther inland. In this place, the distributary channels are modified to form an estuary and elongate tidal bars in the river's mouth; indeed, some of them have been reworked by a wave. The northern lobe is transgressed lobe. The central part of the delta is purely a tidal channel, tidal bar, and possible tidal ridge. Southern distributaries showed the most active fluvial input activity compared to the central and northern parts. In this place, increase in fluvial discharge and a decrease in tidal penetration. Mid bar and triangular bar are developed in the mouth of the river.

The processes taking place in the modern Mahakam delta are just snapshotted in geological time. The situation in the delta today is very likely to have occurred among the many depositional systems in the Serravallian-Tortonian interval. In that time, fluvial, tides, and wave proportion is always dynamic (see Bachtiar, 2004; Arifullah, 2019). As a result, delta and estuary, strand plains, and other non-deltaic elements potentially developed either alternately vertically and sides by the side in that time (Arifullah, 2019).

Figure 1 From the left to the right: ichnofacies distribution, bioturbation index and ichnodiversity maps of Modern Mahakam Delta (Arifullah, 2005).

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In general, the Miocene deposits in the Kutai Basin are fluvial-marine transition zone systems (see Bachtiar, 2004; Arifullah, 2005; Arifullah, 2019) with variations in the depositional elements and dimensions. Fluvial discharge coexists with tidal processes in the river's lower reaches, making it challenging to identify the discrimination of fluvial and tidal processes. Physical sedimentary structures (e.g., Dalrymple and Choi, 2007; Dalrymple et al., 2015) and biogenic sedimentary structures (i.e., ichnofabric by Arifullah et al., 2019) have been developed in the discrimination of both processes.

There are 17 lithofacies codes of Serravallian-Tortonian deposits in the Kutai Basin (Table 1). However, are these lithofacies the unique characteristic of delta deposits? I think lithofacies could also be a feature for estuaries, strand plains, and non-deltaic deposits. Heterolithic lithofacies include flaser, lenticular, ripple cross-stratification with mud-drape, and symmetrical ripples are some indicators for marine deposit. Despite potential debatable (see Table 2), hummocky cross-stratification is believed to indicate marine deposit. Thus, how to discriminate the fluvial, tides, and wave influence based on those lithofacies?

Scale of analysis

Since the high variability of depositional elements and intricate processes in fluvial-marine transition zone vertically and laterally, then the level of analysis is essential to consider. Terms such as *depositional system*, *depositional element*, *depositional environment*, and *facies* are used to mean almost any kind of paleogeomorphic entity. However, using those terms is not essential without an understanding of hierarchy in terms of the scale of the model and their correspondence to the level of analysis.

Interpretation of facies units of ancient sandstone as the deposit of individual channel elements. Also, facies units of interbedding of mudstone and sandstone as the deposit of floodplain element. Both elements are an example of understanding a complex delta plain sequence. This hierarchy has a consequence on the scale of analysis. For example, interpretation of channel elements in terms of bars. Interpretation of bars in terms of bedform migration and aggradation which terms of flow conditions which terms of fluvial regime which in terms of climate and tectonic (Miall, 2006). What is the level of analysis of importance fluvial, tidal, and wave processes by the scale of analysis?

Degree of fluvial, tides and wave domination events include the frequency (mean number of events per period),

Table 1 Lithofacies classification in the Serravallian-Tortonian of Kutai Basin (Arifullah, 2019).

Code	Lithofacies	Sedimentary Structures	Interpretation
C	Coal	Massive, sheets, interbedded with clay	Anoxic condition – swamp
Fr	Silt, clay	Rootlet	Seatearth
Sgc	Gravelly – Coarse Sand	Guttercast	Scourfill
Hm	Silt or clay with sand insert	Bedding, lamination	Suspension dominance interspersed with traction
Hs	Silt or clay insert sand	Bedding, laminate	Traction dominance interspersed with suspension
Mm	Silt or clay	Lamination or massive	Suspension or product of fauna reworking
Se	Sand with scouring	Irregular cross-bedding	Scour fill
Sf	Sand	Synsedimentary fault, microfold	Gravity flow
Sg	Sand	Graded bedding	Gravity flow
Shcs	Sand	Hummocky cross-stratification	Wave and storm
Sl	Sand	Low angle cross-stratification	Antidune
Sp	Sand	Planar cross-bedding	Linguoid, transverse bars, sand waves (low flow regime)
Spm	Sand	Planar cross-bedding with mud drape	Linguoid, transverse bars, sand waves (low flow regime) interspersed with suspension
Sr	Sand	Ripple cross stratification	Ripple migration (traction)
Srm	Sand	Ripple cross-stratification with mud drape	Ripple migration (traction interspersed with suspension)
St	Sand	Trough cross bed	Dunes (upper flow regime).

Table 2 Depositional system where HCS have been reported

Depositional system			References
Continental	Transition	Marine	
Fluvial			Cotter and Graham (1991); Rust and Gibling (1990)
Lacustrine			Eyles and Clark (1986)
	Estuarine-Delta		Arifullah (2005); Arifullah (2019); Bowman and Johnson (2014)
	Intertidal Flat		Yang et al. (2006)
		Shoreface	Dott and Bourgeois (1982); Arifullah (2019)
		Turbidite	Prave and Duke (1990); Monaco (1992); Mulder et al. (2009)
		Pelagic	Seguret et al. (2001)

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return interval (mean time between events), spatial distribution, intensity (physical force of the event per area per time), and impact in a given time interval represented in a particular stratigraphic section. It is in the level of interpretation of river regime (see Anderton, 1985) and behavior of the depositional system which controlled by tectonism, climate change, or base-level change (see Miall, 2014, Table 2.1). Thus, it is related to analysis in the depositional system scale.

Suppose the width of the outcrop in Samarinda ranges from 50 - 150 meters and a height of 7 - 10 meters with a thickness interval of 2.52 - 75 meters. In that case, observations on a single outcrop are simply interpretations of local contexts on a broader scale of paleogeomorphic entities. It could be in one outcrop that the fluvial-dominated and another outcrop correlative with it is a more tidal-dominated is in the same paleogeomorphic entity. Consequently, the level of geological analysis (e.g., ichnology, sedimentology) is the more regional scale, not in the local one.

Today ichnofossil is more important for understanding the importance of fluvial, tidal, and wave processes (Dalrymple et al. 2015; Gugliotta et al. 2015; Arifullah, 2019; Arifullah et al. 2021). Not merely lithofacies characterization does but the mapping of ichnofabric, paleocurrent, paleogeographic and statistical analysis are integrated firmly (Arifullah, 2019). The result is a variety of predictable deposition systems such as estuaries, barrier islands, and strand plains.

Conclusion

The probability of what deposition system develops in the fluvial-marine transition zone depends on the degree of dominance of fluvial processes, tides, and waves. Therefore, it is necessary to map discrimination fluvial, tides, and waves processes. The implication is a new interpretation of the depositional system in the Kutai Basin.

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